

MODE, METHOD AND PROBLEMS IN TEACHING MATHEMATICS IN RELATION TO PROFICIENCY

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Mode, Method and Problems in Teaching Mathematics in Relation to Proficiency

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Abstract

The study aimed to determine the modes and methods of teaching Mathematics and identify the common problems encountered in teaching Mathematics in relation to student's proficiency. One hundred one teachers were the respondents of the study. A standardized questionnaire was used to measure the extent of using the methods in teaching Mathematics. Mean, frequency, Goodman-Kruskall's Gamma and Chi-Square test were the statistical tools used for the analysis of data. The results of the study showed that students received a face-to-face teaching for Algebra and Geometry while modular teaching for Probability and Statistics. Individual and small-group activities are frequently used as teaching methods. The result also showed that the proficiency of students in Probability and Statistics and in Geometry reached a very satisfactory level, and a satisfactory level in Algebra. Overall, the proficiency of students across all subjects was very satisfactory. A significant difference was found in the proficiency of students when taken in terms of mode of teaching used by the Mathematics teachers and no significant difference in the proficiency of students when taken in terms of whole class activities, individual activities, and small group activities. A significant relationship was found between the mode of teaching and the level of proficiency of students while no significant relationship between teaching methods, such as whole class activities, individual activities, and small group activities, and the level of student's proficiency. The themes derived from the challenges encountered by the participants include Solving the Puzzle which reflects the difficulties teachers face in engaging students due to resource constraints; Walking with Constraints which highlights the scarcity of essential learning and teaching resources; and Preparing Students for Lifelong Learning which emphasizes the need to equip students with foundational skills crucial for their future success.

Keywords: *mode, method, problems, proficiency*

Introduction

Mathematics, an essential discipline within primary and secondary schooling, equips learners with foundational abilities and insights necessary for structuring their daily existence (Ariyanti & Santoso, 2020). Despite its importance, students often struggle to appreciate mathematics due to its complex concepts and may find it difficult to understand its relevance to their daily lives. However, mathematics is crucial for developing advanced cognitive skills and the ability to solve problems through calculations, equations, and algorithms, making this knowledge valuable in many areas of life (Magazine, 2022).

Over the years, teaching methods in mathematics have evolved, with traditional methods focusing on memorizing and practicing procedures, while modern approaches emphasize deep understanding of concepts and prioritize student engagement and active learning (Ardeleanu, 2019). Educational strategies for mathematics have recently undergone considerable transformation, moving away from age-old techniques that relied heavily on memorization and constant drills to more progressive approaches that foster deeper comprehension and analytical skills. The adoption of group-based activities, digital resources, and practical problem-solving exercises has been linked to improved student participation and a better understanding of mathematical concepts (Alam, 2023).

Despite these advancements, challenges persist in teaching mathematics. Time constraints remain a significant obstacle for educators, who face the dilemma of covering a vast curriculum within limited time frames. This often hinders students' ability to thoroughly grasp foundational mathematical concepts. As a result, educators are continuously exploring novel strategies to effectively teach mathematics while managing the competing demands of classroom time (Vmlerbenett, 2023).

Therefore, this study aimed to determine the modes and methods of teaching mathematics and analyze how these factors are related to students' proficiency in mathematics. To enrich the discussion, qualitative data were gathered through interviews to provide additional insights into teaching practices and challenges faced by educators.

Research Questions

This study determined the modes and methods of teaching mathematics, identify the common challenges encountered in teaching mathematics in relation to student's proficiency in the Division of Silay City for school year 2023-2024. Specifically, it sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the mode of teaching used by the mathematics teachers?
2. What is the extent of using the methods in teaching in terms of:
 - 2.1. whole class activities;
 - 2.2. individual activities; and
 - 2.3. small group activities?

3. What is the level of proficiency of students when taken as a whole and in terms of:
 - 3.1. algebra;
 - 3.2. geometry; and
 - 3.3. probability and statistics?
4. Is there a significant difference in the proficiency of students when grouped in terms of mode of teaching used by the mathematics teachers?
5. Is there a significant difference in the proficiency of students when grouped in terms of whole class activities, individual activities, and small group activities?
6. Is there a significant relationship between the mode of teaching used by the mathematics teachers and the level of proficiency of students?
7. Is there a significant relationship between the extent of using the methods of teaching in terms of whole class activities, individual activities, and small group activities and the level of proficiency of students?
8. What are the problems encountered by the teachers in teaching Mathematics?

Methodology

Research Design

This study utilized an Embedded Approach, one of the four major types of mixed-methods research designs (Creswell and Plano Clark, 2007) as cited by Boru (2018). The embedded approach involved integrating qualitative data within a primarily quantitative framework to enhance the overall understanding of the research topic. In this study, the quantitative aspect focused on gathering data related to the modes and methods of teaching mathematics and analyzing how these factors related to students' proficiency. Meanwhile, qualitative data on the problems encountered by Mathematics teachers were collected to provide deeper insights and context to the quantitative findings.

The embedded design was well-suited for this study for it combined different types of data to give a fuller picture of teaching problems in mathematics. By using surveys for quantitative data and interviews for qualitative insights, this approach helped to better understand how teaching methods affected student proficiency. It gathered and analyzed data to provide a clearer view of the educational situation being studied (Siedlecki, 2020).

Respondents

The subject and respondents of the study were the Grade 7 to Grade 10 mathematics teachers in the Division of Silay City. As to the proficiency in mathematics, their students who were officially enrolled for SY 2023 – 2024 were also considered as the subject of this study. From the total population of 101 Mathematics teachers, 13 teachers selected using an inclusion criterion participated in interviews to provide deeper insights into the challenges they faced in teaching.

The inclusion criteria for this study required participants to be Grade 7 to Grade 10 Mathematics teachers currently employed in the Division of Silay City for SY 2023–2024, with at least one year of teaching experience in Mathematics. Teachers whose students were officially enrolled in Grade 7 to Grade 10 during the same school year were also included. Additionally, only one teacher from each school who were willing to participate in interviews on the problems they encountered in teaching were considered to ensure meaningful contributions to the study.

Population and Sampling Size

The total population of the Grade 7 to Grade 10 Mathematics teachers in the Division of Silay City for SY 2023 – 2024 was 101. No sample size was computed since the total population was utilized in this study. On the next page shows the distribution of the respondents per grade level.

Table 1. *Population of the Math Teachers and Group of Students per Grade Level*

<i>Grade Level</i>	<i>Teachers</i>	<i>Group of students</i>
Grade 7	22	22
Grade 8	24	24
Grade 9	26	26
Grade 10	29	29
Total	101	101

Instrument

In this study, an adopted questionnaire developed by Bautista and Del Valle (2023) on their study entitled “Communicative competence and oral language usage of Filipino learners in English. International Journal of Educational Management and Development Studies” for the method of teaching. It was divided on three categories, the whole class activities, individual activities and small group activities. The whole class activities has 11 indicators, the individual activities has 30 indicators and the small group activities has 15 indicators.

Each category has 5 options where 1 = never, 2 = hardly ever, 3 = sometimes, 4 = often, and 5 = very often. The mode of teaching has 2 options which are face-to-face and modular. This was based on the OASOPS No. 2023-077 issued last 20 April 2023, and OUCT and OUOPS Memorandum dated 28 February 2023 (Implementation of Alternative Delivery Mode (ADM) in All Public Elementary and Secondary Schools), DepEd has given the school heads the authority and discretion to suspend the conduct of in-person classes and shift to alternative delivery modes (ADM) in cases of extreme heat and other calamities that may compromise the health and safety of learners, teachers, and non-teaching personnel. The proficiency of the students were taken from their grades in Algebra, Geometry and Probability and Statistics of SY 2023-2024. Additionally, the researcher employed a semi-structured interview guide to gather qualitative insights from the participating teachers on the problems they encounter in teaching mathematics.

Procedure

The researcher started the conduct of the study by sending the letter of intent to the Schools Division Superintendent asking permission to conduct the said study (see Appendix D). Upon approval, the researcher personally conducted the survey questionnaires to the respondents of the study. The data were retrieved immediately, checked, recorded and were subjected to appropriate statistical computation and analyses using SPSS.

Data Analysis

In the analyses and interpretation of data, different statistical tools were used:

To answer the first statement of the problem which is to determine the mode of teaching used by the Mathematics teachers, frequency and percent distribution were used.

To answer the second statement of the problem which is to determine the extent of using the teaching methods in terms of whole class activities, individual activities, and small group activities, mean was used.

To answer the third statement of the problem which is to determine the level of proficiency of students when taken as a whole and in terms of Algebra, Geometry, and Statistics, mean was used.

To answer the fourth statement of the problem which is to determine if there is a significant difference in the proficiency of students when grouped in terms of mode of teaching used by the Mathematics teachers, Mann Whitney (U) test was used.

To answer the fifth statement of the problem which is to determine if there is a significant difference in the proficiency of students when grouped in terms of whole class activities, individual activities, and small group activities, Kruskal Wallis (H) test was used.

To answer the sixth statement of the problem which is to determine if there is a significant relationship between the mode of teaching used by the Mathematics teachers and the level of proficiency of students, Chi-square test was used.

To answer the seventh statement of the problem which is to determine if there is a significant relationship between the extent of using the methods in teaching in terms of whole class activities, individual activities, and small group activities and the level of proficiency of students, Gamma coefficient was used.

To answer the ninth statement of the problem which is to determine the common problems encountered by the teachers in teaching Mathematics, Patton's 4 Steps in Analyzing Data was used to thematize the essential statements taken from the interview.

Results and Discussion

This section underscores the presentation, analysis, and interpretation of the data gathered in this research study. The results are presented in tables to emphasize the significant meaning of each problem.

Mode of Teaching used by the Mathematics Teachers

The table below presents the mode of teaching used by the Mathematics teachers.

Table 2. *Frequency and Percent Distribution of the Mode of Teaching used by the Mathematics Teachers in Three Learning Areas*

<i>Learning Areas</i>	<i>Mode of Teaching</i>	<i>f</i>	<i>%</i>
Algebra	Face to Face	101	100.00
	Modular	0	0.00
	Total	101	100.00
Geometry	Face to Face	101	100.00
	Modular	0	0.00
	Total	101	100.00
Probability and Statistics	Face to Face	0	0.00
	Modular	101	100.00
	Total	101	100.00

Table 2 shows the teaching modes used by the mathematics teachers for Algebra, Geometry, and Probability and Statistics. One hundred one mathematics teachers used face-to-face teaching in Algebra and Geometry and used modular mode of teaching in learning Probability and Statistics. This shows that students learn algebra and geometry in person, they listen and talked with teachers and classmates and gets feedback right away. In contrast, students who received modular learning for Probability and Statistics learn at their own pace and are flexible, which suits the complex and theoretical nature of these subjects.

The result of this study aligns with the Education Hub's findings (2023) which highlight the substantial benefits of in-person education due to its focus on interpersonal interaction. In a conventional classroom environment, students have the opportunity to engage directly with teachers, fostering immediate and dynamic interaction. This active engagement not only enhances understanding, participation, and motivation but also allows students to ask questions, resolve uncertainties, and receive prompt feedback from teachers, thereby enriching their overall learning journey.

Additionally, modular teaching is recognized as a highly effective approach in basic education. This method empowers students to learn at their own pace and take ownership of their learning process by understanding their specific learning objectives, often without relying solely on textbooks and other traditional resources (Guardian, 2020).

Extent of Using the Teaching Methods

The table 3 presents the extent of using the teaching methods in terms of whole class activities, individual activities, and small group activities.

Table 3. *Extent of Using the Teaching Methods in Terms of Whole Class Activities, Individual Activities, and Small Group Activities*

<i>Teaching Method</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
Whole Class Activities	3.18	Moderate Extent
Individual Activities	3.91	High Extent
Small Group Activities	3.85	High Extent

The table shows that individual activities and small group activities are used at a high extent, with a mean of 3.91 and 3.85, respectively. Whole-class activities are used at a moderate extent, with a mean score of 3.18.

This suggests that teachers prioritize personalized and interactive learning. The common use of individual and small group activities indicates a focus on addressing individual student needs and fostering teamwork. This method can boost student engagement, provide customized instruction, and enhance critical thinking skills. However, the less frequent use of whole-class activities highlights the need to balance teaching methods for the benefit of all students.

This finding is in consonance with the claim of Litera Centre (2021) that individualized teaching significantly enhances students' enjoyment of the subject matter and their ability to grasp concepts effectively. By focusing solely on the student, the teacher aims to improve their skills. This method allows students to learn at their own pace, unlike traditional classroom settings where the teaching speed is adjusted according to the majority's understanding. This personalized approach improves comprehension and memory retention, fosters a more positive learning environment, and boosts student motivation and engagement. Ultimately, it leads to better academic outcomes and helps students reach their full potential.

Moreover, small-group teaching creates an ideal environment where students can digest, analyze, and combine ideas from lectures and textbooks. It is particularly effective for tackling complex concepts that can significantly enhance their understanding of a subject. This teaching method is distinct because it encourages active participation and typically involves groups of eight to twelve students. Students can practice, learn from mistakes, and develop their own perspectives on the material they are studying. This hands-on approach supports deeper learning, allowing students to truly master the content rather than just repeat it (UCL, 2019).

Level of Proficiency of Students When Taken as a Whole and In Terms of Algebra, Geometry and Probability and Statistics

The table below presents the level of proficiency of students when taken as a whole and in terms of Algebra, Geometry, and Probability and Statistics.

Table 4. *Level of Proficiency of Students When Taken as a Whole and in terms of Algebra, Geometry, and Probability and Statistics*

<i>Level of Student's Proficiency in terms of Learning Areas</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
Algebra	84.43	Satisfactory
Geometry	85.73	Very Satisfactory
Probability and Statistics	87.47	Very Satisfactory
As a Whole	85.87	Very Satisfactory

The table shows the level of proficiency of students in terms of different learning areas and their overall proficiency. The level of proficiency of students in Probability and Statistics and Geometry are very satisfactory with a mean of 87.47 and 85.73, respectively.

The proficiency of students in Algebra is satisfactory with a mean score of 84.43. As a whole, the level of proficiency of students is very satisfactory with a mean of 85.87.

The result implies that students have shown strong proficiency in Geometry and in Probability and Statistics, achieving high scores that are considered very satisfactory. While their proficiency in Algebra is satisfactory which indicates potential for improvement compared to Geometry and Probability and Statistics. Overall, students have performed well across these subjects, demonstrating a solid grasp of mathematical concepts and their practical application.

The results align with Bearneza's (2021) study which found that students performed at an average level in Algebra due to their mastery of five key areas: signed numbers, arithmetic, fractions, exponents, and factors. This proficiency in algebraic skills led to good grades and overall academic success in mathematics. The students' average level of algebra skills suggests they had a solid understanding of these areas and could apply their knowledge with minimal assistance from teachers or peers.

In contrast, the results diverge from the study of Duterte et al. (2024) which found that students' abilities in Statistics and Probability were rated as fair. This implies that mastering Statistics and Probability is notably more difficult compared to other subjects. Students exhibit poor performance in these areas and hold negative attitudes toward the subject, indicating a lack of confidence in tackling statistical and probabilistic problems (Ailton et al., 2018).

Additionally, the results contradict Flores' (2019) study on students' academic performance in Geometry, which revealed scores classified as below average. A below-average performance signifies a partial mastery of fundamental skills in the subject, possibly linked to the students' negative attitudes toward Geometry.

Difference in the Proficiency of Students in terms of Mode of Teaching

The table below illustrates the difference in the proficiency of students in terms of mode of teaching used by the Mathematics teachers.

Table 5. *Difference in the Proficiency of Students in terms of Mode of Teaching*

<i>Mode of Teaching</i>	<i>n</i>	<i>Mean Rank</i>
Face to Face	101	81.82
Modular	101	87.47

Computed value (U) : 3113.00

P-value : <0.001

Decision : Reject Ho

Interpretation : Significant at 0.05 significance level

The table reveals that the proficiency of students in the face to face mode of teaching has a mean rank of 81.82 and a mean rank of 87.47 in the modular teaching. Using Mann Whitney (U) test, its computed value is 3113.00 and its p-value is <0.001 which is lower than 0.05 level of significance. Thus, the null hypotheses is rejected. This means that there is a significant difference in the proficiency of students in terms of mode of teaching used by the Mathematics teachers.

The result implies that the mode of teaching has a significant impact in the proficiency of students. Adopting modular teaching methods could lead to improved student proficiency in Mathematics. Students have a better proficiency in their subjects taken under the modular class compare to their performance in their subject taken under the face to face class. This is because they have enough time to research their lesson, to comply their assigned tasks and to answer their activities or quizzes. Unlike in the face to face class where they have a time limit for every activity or quiz in a particular subject.

The findings of this study is in agreement to the statement of Cañales (2021) that in Mathematics, students supported the use of a modular distance learning method, citing several benefits. They acknowledged that while there were some minor challenges, their academic performance improved with this approach. The modular distance learning technique significantly enhanced their understanding of Mathematics. According to percentage grade indicators, their academic achievement was notably high. This improvement can be attributed to the ability to revisit and review the modules whenever they needed to reinforce concepts that were not fully understood.

In contrary, Dangle and Somaoang (2020) stated that some students could not complete their modules on time because they spent much of their study time helping their siblings with their studies and assisting their parents with work. Teachers believed that the students' responses lacked validity and that achieving mastery of the subjects was unlikely. Parents often could not help their children due to a lack of knowledge, with some parents not having completed their own education. Additionally, some teachers had poor cellphone reception, and they were overwhelmed with paperwork to review and record.

Difference in the Proficiency of Students in terms of Whole Class Activities

The table on the next page shows the difference in the proficiency of students in terms of whole class activities.

As shown in Table 6, students who perceive the use the whole class activities at a very high extent has a mean rank of 80.50 in their proficiency, those who observe a high extent has a mean rank of 47.52, those who perceive a moderate extent has a mean rank of 52.92, and those who note a low extent has a mean rank of 24.17.

Table 6. *Difference in the Proficiency of Students in terms of Whole Class Activities*

<i>Extent of Whole Class Activities</i>	<i>n</i>	<i>Mean Rank</i>
Very High Extent	1	80.50
High Extent	25	47.52
Moderate Extent	72	52.92
Low Extent	3	24.17
Very low Extent	0	0.00

Computed value (H): 4.26
P-value: 0.235
Decision: Accept H_0
Interpretation: Not significant at 0.05 significance level

Using a Kruskal Wallis (H) test, the computed value is 4.26 and a p-value of 0.235 is higher than 0.05 level of significance. Therefore, the null hypothesis is accepted. This means that there is no significant difference in the proficiency of students when taken in terms of whole class activities.

The result implies that the extent of whole-class activities does not significantly affect students' proficiency levels. Regardless of how extensive the whole-class activities are, proficiency levels remain relatively consistent across different activity extents. This is because the whole class activities unites teachers and students, and they shared goals in a common space, using direct instruction to foster a collaborative learning environment. This activities encourages a sense of community, with everyone working toward the same objectives.

The findings of this study is in disagreement to the statement of Drew (2024) that whole class discussion is a teaching strategy where all students participate in a group dialogue about a specific topic. This approach ensures that every student receives the same information and encourages participation in a democratic setting. Conducting lessons as a whole group helps to prevent knowledge gaps and avoids diluting information for some students, as might happen in smaller groups.

Also, the result is in contrast with the claim of Gustafsson (2023) that whole-class discussions have demonstrated the capacity to enhance students' learning and foster positive attitudes toward mathematics. However, truly productive whole-class mathematical discussions, where students can significantly advance their understanding, remain infrequent in classrooms.

Difference in the Proficiency of Students in terms of Individual Activities

The table below shows the difference in the proficiency of students in terms of individual activities.

Table 7. *Difference in the Proficiency of Students in terms of Individual Activities*

<i>Extent of Individual Activities</i>	<i>n</i>	<i>Mean Rank</i>
Very great	8	47.00
Great	90	52.03
Moderate	3	30.83
Low	0	0.00
Very low	0	0.00

Computed value (H): 1.71
P-value: 0.426
Decision: Accept H_0
Interpretation: Not significant at 0.05 significance level

As shown in the table, the proficiency of students who observe that they use the individual activities at a very great extent has a mean rank of 47.00, those who identify a great extent has a mean rank of 52.03 and those who perceive a moderate extent has a mean rank of 30.83.

Using a Kruskal Wallis (H) test, the computed value is 1.71 and a p-value of 0.426 is greater than 0.05 level of significance. Thus, the null hypothesis is accepted. This means that there is no significant difference in the proficiency of students when taken in terms of individual activities.

The result implies that the level of individual activities does not significantly influence students' proficiency; whether students engage in individual activities to a great or moderate extent, their proficiency levels remain similar. This could suggest that factors other than the degree of participation in individual activities may play a more critical role in determining students' overall proficiency.

The findings of this study is in contrast with the traditional one-size-fits-all approach to education, highlighting the effectiveness of individualized instruction in meeting the unique needs of each student. This method tailors teaching to focus on one specific area at a time, either as a standalone strategy or as part of a broader differentiated teaching approach. Students benefit from receiving concentrated help from teachers, allowing them to grasp and master new concepts. For some, this means delving deeper into challenging material, while others can skip ahead to more advanced topics if they already understand the foundational concepts (Osewalt, 2023).

By aligning teaching methods with individual learning styles, personalized instruction enhances understanding and memory retention.

This approach also fosters a more engaging and supportive learning environment, boosting student motivation and involvement. Ultimately, individualized instruction leads to improved academic outcomes, helping students reach their full potential. Research consistently shows that every student is different, making individualized teaching a logical choice for promoting growth. Furthermore, learning should be an engaging experience rather than a forced one, and individualized instruction significantly contributes to making students enjoy the subject matter and effectively grasp concepts (Litera Centre, 2021).

Difference in the Proficiency of Students in terms of Small Group Activities

The table below presents the difference in the proficiency of students when taken in terms of small group activities.

Table 8. *Difference in the Proficiency of Students when taken in terms of Small Group Activities*

<i>Extent of Whole Class Activities</i>	<i>n</i>	<i>Mean Rank</i>
Very great	5	75.90
Great	90	49.55
Moderate	6	52.00
Low	0	0
Very low	0	0

Computed value (H): 3.90
P-value: 0.142
Decision: Accept Ho
Interpretation: Not significant at 0.05 significance level

The table reveals that the proficiency of students when taken in terms of small group activities, those who perceive that they use the whole class activities at a very great extent has a mean rank of 75.90, those who recognize a great extent has a mean rank of 49.55 and those who observe a moderate extent has a mean rank of 52.00.

Using a Kruskal Wallis (H) test, the computed value is 3.90 and a p-value of 0.142 is greater than 0.05 level of significance. For this reason, the null hypothesis is accepted. This means that there is no significant difference in the proficiency of students when taken in terms of small group activities.

The findings of Byiringiro (2023) are in contrast to the result of this study. He claimed that students learn best through hands-on experiences. In a demonstration and discussion approach, dynamic interaction between students and teachers is emphasized. Cooperative group work helps students exchange information, develop new perspectives, and communicate socially.

Learning in small groups places students at the forefront of their education, allowing them to actively engage with the material rather than passively observe. In these settings, students can collaboratively discuss and work through mathematical concepts, fostering confidence and encouraging them to articulate their thoughts without the pressure of addressing the entire class. This dynamic promotes meaningful conversations about math as students focus on the tasks at hand, making the learning experience more interactive and hands-on (Ali, 2023).

Relationship Between the Mode of Teaching

Used by the Mathematics Teachers and the Level of Proficiency of Students

The table on the next page illustrates the relationship between the mode of teaching used by the Mathematics teachers and the level of proficiency of students.

Table 9. *Relationship Between the Mode of Teaching Used by the Mathematics Teachers and the Level of Proficiency of Students*

<i>Mode of Teaching</i>	<i>Level of Proficiency of Students</i>					<i>Total</i>
	<i>Outstanding</i>	<i>Very Satisfactory</i>	<i>Satisfactory</i>	<i>Fairly Satisfactory</i>	<i>Did Not Meet Expectations</i>	
Face to Face	5	50	46	0	0	101
Modular	33	47	20	1	0	101
Total	38	97	66	1	0	202

Computed value (x2): 31.97
P-value: <0.001
Decision: Reject Ho
Interpretation: Significant at 0.05 significance level

The table reveals that 38 students have an outstanding level of performance, with five who received a face-to-face teaching and 33 who received modular. Ninety-seven students have a very satisfactory level of performance, with 50 received a face-to-face and 47 received a modular mode of teaching. Sixty-six students have a satisfactory level of performance, with 46 received a face-to-face and 20 received a modular mode of teaching. However, one student has a fairly satisfactory level of performance and received a modular mode of teaching.

Using the Chi-square (x2), the data revealed a computed value of 31.97 and a p-value of <0.001 which is lower than the 0.05 level of significance. Thus, the null hypothesis was rejected. This means that there is a significant relationship between the mode of teaching

and the level of performance of students. This implies that the mode of teaching significantly influences the performance of students in Mathematics.

The findings of this study is in consonance with the statement of o Carreon et al. (2022) that face-to-face learning was the preferred method for students before the advent of online learning systems. Students view face-to-face mathematics learning positively, feeling more comfortable communicating with classmates in a classroom environment. This mode of instruction enhances their ability to learn and perform well in mathematics.

The result is also similar to the findings of Salapuddin (2021) which emphasizes that the Modular Learning Modality significantly influences mathematics achievement, serving as an effective teaching strategy that leads to a very satisfactory level of performance. Additionally, Oco and Comahig (2023) found in their study that students' mathematics performance using both synchronous online learning and modular distance learning strategies was highly satisfactory, showing significant improvement between pretest and posttest results.

Relationship Between the Level of Proficiency and the Extent of Whole Class Activities

The table below presents the relationship between the extent of whole class activities and the level of proficiency of students.

Table 10. *Relationship Between the Extent of Whole Class Activities and the Level of Proficiency*

Extent of Whole Class Activities	Level of Student's Proficiency					Total
	Outstanding	Very Satisfactory	Satisfactory	Fairly Satisfactory	Did Not Meet Expectations	
Very High Extent	0	1	0	0	0	1
High Extent	5	8	11	1	0	25
Moderate Extent	2	48	22	0	0	72
Low Extent	0	0	3	0	0	3
Very Low Extent	0	0	0	0	0	0
Total	7	57	36	1	0	101

Computed value (G): 0.07

p-value: 0.712

Decision: Accept H_0

Interpretation: Not significant at 0.05 significance level

Table 10 shows that out of 72 group of students who have a moderate extent of whole-class activities, 48 have a very satisfactory level of performance, 22 have a satisfactory level, and two have an outstanding level. Among the 25 students who have a high extent of whole-class activities, 11 have a satisfactory level of performance, eight have a very satisfactory level, five have an outstanding level, and one has a fairly satisfactory level. It can also be noted that three group of students have a low extent of whole-class activities and a satisfactory level of performance. Only one group of student has a very high extent of whole-class activities and a very satisfactory level of performance.

Using the Goodman-Kruskal's Gamma (G), the data revealed a computed value of 0.07 and a p-value of 0.712 which is higher than the 0.05 level of significance. Thus, the null hypothesis was accepted.

This means that there is no significant relationship between the extent of whole-class activities and level of performance of students. This implies that the extent of whole-class activities does not significantly influence their performance.

The data challenges Gustafsson's (2023) suggestion that whole-class instruction enhances students' learning and fosters positive attitudes toward mathematics. According to Meador (2019), whole-group instruction provides a valuable opportunity to review and sustain proficiency in skills that students have already mastered.

Relationship Between the Extent of Individual Activities and Level of Proficiency of Students

Table 11 on then next page presents the relationship between the extent of individual activities and level of proficiency of students.

Table 11. *Relationship Between the Extent of Individual Activities and the Level of Proficiency of Students*

Extent of Individual Activities	Level of Proficiency of Students					Total
	Outstanding	Very Satisfactory	Satisfactory	Fairly Satisfactory	Did Not Meet Expectations	
Very High Extent	0	5	3	0	0	8
High Extent	7	51	31	1	0	90
Moderate Extent	0	1	2	0	0	3
Low Extent	0	0	0	0	0	0
Very Low Extent	0	0	0	0	0	0
Total	7	57	36	1	0	101

Computed value (G): 0.09

p-value: 0.741

Decision: Accept H_0

Interpretation: Not significant at 0.05 significance level

Table 11 revealed that out of 90 students who have a high extent of individual activities, 51 have a very satisfactory level of performance, 31 are satisfactory, seven are outstanding, and one has a fairly satisfactory level of proficiency. Eight group of students have a very high extent of individual activities, of which five groups have a very satisfactory level and three groups have a satisfactory level of proficiency. Only three group of students have a moderate extent of individual activities in which two have a satisfactory level and one has a very satisfactory level of proficiency.

Using the Goodman-Kruskal’s Gamma (G), the data revealed a computed value of 0.09 and a p-value of 0.741 which is higher than the 0.05 level of significance. Thus, the null hypothesis was accepted. This means that there is no significant relationship between the extent of individual activities and level of proficiency of students. This implies that the extent of individual activities does not significantly influence their proficiency in Mathematics.

These results contradict with Matic Education Expert (2021) which states that independent math work is essential for successful math instruction because it enables students to practice and apply what they have learned in small groups. Without this independent practice, students cannot fully master math concepts and skills. Individualization, as a key teaching strategy, can improve students' attitudes toward math and enhance their performance.

Relationship Between the Extent of Small Group Activities and Level of Proficiency of Students

Table 12 below shows the relationship between the extent of small group activities and the level of proficiency.

Table 12. Relationship Between the Extent of Small Group Activities and the Level of Proficiency of Students

Extent of Small Group Activities	Level of Proficiency of Students					Total
	Outstanding	Very Satisfactory	Satisfactory	Fairly Satisfactory	Did Not Meet Expectations	
Very High Extent	0	5	0	0	0	5
High Extent	6	50	33	1	0	90
Moderate Extent	1	2	3	0	0	6
Low Extent	0	0	0	0	0	0
Very Low Extent	0	0	0	0	0	0
Total	7	57	36	1	0	101

Computed value (G): 0.32
 p-value: 0.258
 Decision: Accept Ho
 Interpretation: Not significant at 0.05 significance level

The table reveals that out of 90 students with a high extent of small group activities, 50 have a very satisfactory level of proficiency, 33 have a satisfactory level, six have an outstanding level, and only one has a fairly satisfactory level. Six group of students have a moderate extent of small group activities, of which three have a satisfactory level, two have a very satisfactory level, and one has an outstanding level of proficiency. Five group of students obtained a very high extent of small group activities and a very satisfactory level of proficiency.

Using the Goodman-Kruskal’s Gamma (G), the data revealed a computed value of 0.32 and a p-value of 0.258 which is higher than the 0.05 level of significance. Thus, the null hypothesis was accepted. This means that there is no significant relationship between the extent of small group activities and level of proficiency of students. This implies that the extent of small group activities does not significantly influence their proficiency in Mathematics.

The results diverge from Muchiri and Njenga (2020) who found that small group activities can be a powerful tool for teaching and learning mathematics. According to their research, the effectiveness of small group work largely depends on the grouping strategy used. Effective grouping promotes respect, equity, positive relationships, and maximum participation among students. Regardless of the desired outcome, the right grouping strategy always positively impacts mathematics education and students' proficiency.

Problems Encountered by Mathematics Teachers

The qualitative analysis revealed several significant themes regarding the problems faced by Mathematics teachers, which are essential for understanding the complexities of teaching in the current educational landscape. These themes: Solving the Puzzle, Walking with Constraints, and Preparing Students for Lifelong Learning, presents the multifaceted nature of the difficulties encountered in the teaching and learning process.

Theme 1: Solving the Puzzle

The challenges related to student engagement in mathematics resemble a complex puzzle that teachers must piece together to create an effective learning environment. Teachers across various schools reported difficulties in maintaining the interest and motivation of their students.

One teacher from School 1 expressed that engaging all students effectively in face-to-face settings proved to be a significant challenge. This sentiment was echoed by another teacher from the same school, who noted that modular teaching also struggled with keeping students motivated. The short attention spans of students were particularly concerning, as mentioned by a teacher from School 5, who

highlighted those students often lose focus during lessons. This issue was further compounded by frequent distractions caused by peers, as indicated by a participant from School 12. Additionally, a lack of parental support during distance learning was identified as a major obstacle by a teacher from School 8, suggesting that engagement challenges extend beyond the classroom to involve family dynamics. The difficulties in classroom management also emerged as a notable concern, with a teacher from School 11 identifying it as one of the key challenges that impede effective teaching. These findings underscore the need for innovative strategies to foster student engagement, particularly in light of technological distractions and varying levels of interest in learning.

The theme highlights the intricate nature of fostering student interest in mathematics, which indicates that educators need to enhance the learning experience to improve student outcomes. Research shows a moderately strong and positive correlation between overall student engagement and academic achievement, with behavioral, emotional, and cognitive engagement also demonstrating positive correlations (Lei et al., 2018). This suggests that when educators prioritize student engagement through innovative teaching strategies, they are likely to enhance academic performance and foster a more enriching educational environment.

Theme 2: Walking with Constraints

The theme “Walking with Constraints” captures the journey of teaching within the bounds of limited resources, where teachers continuously navigate and adapt to shortages. Many educators reported inadequate access to essential educational resources, such as textbooks, technological tools, and teaching aids, which hindered effective instruction, as noted by a teacher from School 2. Additionally, the challenge of high absenteeism disrupted the continuity of learning, making it difficult to maintain a structured curriculum. Students in remote areas faced added obstacles, including outdated or incomplete materials, which impeded their learning progress, as observed by another teacher from School 2.

In face-to-face learning environments, the scarcity of math textbooks limited lesson planning and teaching, as highlighted by a teacher from School 3. In technology-dependent settings, some students lacked access to gadgets, rendering them unable to complete assignments, as experienced by teachers in Schools 4 and 5. Similarly, internet connectivity issues affected students’ ability to participate fully in activities, which teachers from Schools 5 and 7 recognized as a significant barrier. Outdated or malfunctioning technology also caused delays at critical moments, as reported by a teacher from School 12.

The reliance on borrowed materials further restricted students’ learning experiences, particularly in hands-on activities, as described by a teacher from School 6. Additionally, insufficient teaching aids and manipulatives hindered practical learning, especially in mathematics, as noted by a teacher from School 9. These resource limitations collectively emphasize the urgent need for schools to enhance support systems and ensure that all students have access to the necessary materials for effective learning. Phajane (2023) stresses that providing teachers with adequate training and resources, along with an ideal teacher-to-learner ratio of 1:30, is essential for curriculum success. Furthermore, Diba et al. (2023) underscore the importance of strengthening support systems and supplying critical materials, both of which would address these limitations and enrich the learning experience for all students.

Theme 3: Preparing Students for Lifelong Learning

The last theme “Preparing Students for Lifelong Learning” emphasizes the importance of equipping students with essential skills, such as mathematical skills, that serve as a foundation for future success. However, a common problem being encountered is that many students enter the classroom without a solid grounding in foundational skills. This lack of preparedness hampers their ability to keep pace with current grade-level content which affects not only their progress but also the overall effectiveness of teaching. Teachers have noted that without these core competencies, students struggle to engage with more advanced material which underscores the critical need for strong academic preparedness.

A teacher from School 3 observed that unmastered competencies from previous grade levels greatly affected students’ learning trajectories, noting that the lack of foundational skills in mathematics hampers their ability to keep pace with the current curriculum. Furthermore, issues such as students’ reluctance to read or study their modules, highlighted by a teacher from School 6, were cited as barriers to meaningful learning. Many teachers expressed concerns about the varying skill levels among students, which complicates instruction; a teacher from School 9 noted that varying skill levels and learning styles lead to complicated teaching dynamics. This diversity in preparedness often results in significant disparities in performance, as described by a teacher from School 10, who emphasized that students’ differing educational backgrounds contribute to these variations.

Moreover, learners’ difficulties with mathematics, such as appearing mentally exhausted during math tasks and lacking mastery of number facts, were noted by a teacher from School 7. Another teacher from School 8 remarked that students struggle to master basic operations, which prolongs the time required to cover these foundational concepts. Some students’ reluctance to ask questions, as mentioned by a teacher from School 5, further affects their understanding of mathematical concepts. Additionally, frequent changes in the curriculum create confusion and hinder effective teaching, as noted by a participant from School 11. Collectively, these problems emphasize the critical importance of establishing a strong foundational understanding in mathematics and highlight the need for tailored instructional approaches that accommodate the diverse learning needs of students, including addressing the lack of foundational skills in younger learners, as noted by a teacher from School 12.

The problems from different levels of academic preparedness, worsened by recent changes in the DepEd curriculum and the shift to

modular learning, highlight the urgent need for focused interventions to strengthen foundational math skills. Addressing these gaps is essential to support all students effectively in their learning journey, as accelerated and corequisite developmental math courses lead to more positive academic outcomes compared to traditional developmental math courses; however, modularized courses do not (Boatman, 2021).

Conclusions

Based on the findings of the study, the following conclusions were created.

Students received a face-to-face teaching for Algebra and Geometry while modular teaching for Probability and Statistics.

Individual and small-group activities are frequently used as teaching methods.

Students demonstrated a strong proficiency across the subjects of Algebra, Geometry, and Probability and Statistics.

The proficiency of students is better using modular teaching compare to face to face mode of teaching.

The proficiency of students in terms of whole class activities, individual activities, and small group activities do not significantly vary.

The students' proficiency levels are significantly impacted by the mode of teaching.

The students' proficiency in Mathematics is not influenced by the teaching methods used by the teachers.

These themes underscore the problems teachers face in the current DepEd landscape which emphasize the need for enhanced support and resources to boost student engagement and learning outcomes.

With reference to the findings and conclusions of the study, the following recommendations are offered:

Teachers may consider tailoring their teaching methods to align with students' preferences, such as opting for face-to-face instruction in Algebra and Geometry and modular teaching in Statistics and Probability, based on specific subject needs.

Teachers can improve their teaching strategies by focusing on individual and small-group activities, which are commonly used and have the potential to actively engage students in the learning process.

Schools and teachers may develop strategies to address the most prevalent challenges, which are student related. By focusing on these challenges, they can create a more effective learning environment. Additionally, efforts can be made to reduce teacher-related challenges, which also impact the effectiveness of both face-to-face and modular teaching. By addressing both student and teacher-related issues, schools can enhance the overall educational experience.

Students are encouraged to maintain and further develop their performance by actively engaging in class. It is also recommended that teachers continuously assess and provide support to help students maintain their very satisfactory performance level in Mathematics.

It is recommended that educators blend face-to-face and modular teaching approaches to improve student proficiency. This combination can help address varying learning needs and adapt to different educational settings. Such flexibility in teaching modes may lead to better overall performance.

School administrators need to consider how teaching methods affect student performance. By designing curriculum thoughtfully and using effective teaching strategies, they can improve learning outcomes. Teachers may adapt their methods to match student preferences, like using face-to-face teaching for Algebra and Geometry and modular teaching for Statistics and Probability, to better meet subject-specific needs.

Though performance in Mathematics is not significantly influenced by the teaching methods used, teachers may focus on other factors that affect student outcomes, such as teaching quality, student motivation, and resource availability. They can also continue to explore innovative teaching approaches that cater to diverse learning styles and preferences.

To boost student proficiency, it is helpful to look beyond the challenges teachers face. Improving teaching methods, offering extra resources, and using targeted support strategies can make a bigger difference in student performance. Also, exploring other factors that might affect student proficiency could provide more insights into addressing any issues.

For future researchers, it is recommended to expand the scope of research to include qualitative methods, such as interviews and focus groups, to gain deeper insights into the experiences and perceptions of students and teachers regarding different teaching modes and methods.

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